

Cyclic voltammetric reduction of amino acid ketimine and its Co(II) complex

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Abstract : The electrochemical behavior of amino acid ketimine synthesized by the condensation of 4-methylacetophenone and glycine (1 : 1 molar ratio) was further treated with cobalt(II) acetate (2 : 1 molar ratio) to form Co^{II}-ketimine complex has been studied in two different medium (DMF and CH₃OH) on glassy carbon electrode (GCE) using cyclic voltammetric technique. The kinetic parameters like cathodic peak potential E_{pc} , cathodic peak current I_{pc} , charge-transfer coefficient α_n , diffusion coefficient $D_0^{1/2}$ and rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$ have been calculated. The electrode process was shown to be diffusion controlled and irreversible. The effect of sweep rate, pH, concentration and change in buffer was evaluated.

Keywords : Amino acids, ketimine, cyclic voltammetry, charge transfer coefficient (α_n), diffusion coefficient ($D_0^{1/2}$), rate constant ($K_{f,h}^\circ$).

Introduction

Cyclic voltammetry is the most widely used technique for acquiring qualitative information about electrochemical reactions. The power of cyclic voltammetry results from its ability to rapidly provide considerable information on the thermodynamics of redox processes and the kinetics of heterogeneous electron-transfer reactions, and on coupled chemical reactions or adsorption processes¹. Cyclic voltammetry is often the first experiment performed in an electroanalytical study. In particular, it offers a rapid location of redox potentials of the electro active species, and convenient evaluation of the effect of media upon the redox process. Complexes containing Schiff bases have not only found extensive application in design and synthesis of organic molecules², but these compounds exhibit several of significant electrical conductivity, host-guest chemistry³, sensors⁴, biological activity⁵ and analytical applications⁶⁻¹⁰. A number of Schiff base derivatives have shown interesting biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, anticonvulsant, antimalarial, and anticancer¹¹⁻¹⁴. In recent years Schiff base ligands received enormous attention due to their wide application in the field catalyst¹⁵, anti-microbial, anti-tumors activity¹⁶ and recently reported as nano sized Schiff

base complexes for medical applications¹⁷. Their prompt and everlasting widespread certainly arose from the ease with which they can be synthesized, their staggering variety and their vast complexing formed. Although several properties of these Schiff base complexes well known, it remains the novel and application for such a peculiar class of molecules¹⁸. Schiff base of the transition complexes containing tetradentate ligands have obvious redox active properties.

In this paper we are representing synthesis, spectral analysis, cyclic voltammetric studies and antimicrobial activity of such type of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine (GMAPI) and its Co^{II} complex.

Preparation of ketimine :

Ketimine has been synthesized by condensing the ethanolic solution of glycine amino acid and 4-methylacetophenone. The condensation product was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, recrystallized with ethanol, and dried under reduced pressure¹⁹. The purity and characteristics of the amino acid-ketimine was examined by elemental analysis and spectral data.

GMAPI : Colour cream, yield : 76%, Calcd. : C, 67.12; H, 7.95; N, 7.6; O, 20.2. Found : C, 65.98; H, 7.05; N, 7.00; O, 19.98%; Mol. wt. Calcd. :

Scheme 1. Synthesis of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine (GMAPI).

400.20, Found : 400.47.

Synthesis of complex :

The Co^{II} complex has been prepared by mixing the methanolic solution of Co^{II} acetate (0.015 mole) and methanolic solution of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine (GMAPI). The resulting mixture was then refluxed on water bath for 4–5 h. The complex formed was filtered, recrystallized with ethanol, finally washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), and dried under reduced pressure.

C₂₃H₃₂CoN₂O₆ : Pink solid; yield 78%; Calcd. : C, 58.22; H, 7.00; Co, 12.02; N, 5.82; O, 20.2. Found : C, 56.21; H, 6.56; Co, 11.99; N, 5.70; O, 19.53%; Mol. wt. Calcd. : 491.16, Found : 491.44.

Cyclic voltammetric study of GMAPI and its Co complex :

Glassy carbon electrode was cleaned prior to the each experiment polishing with 0.1 μm alumina on a polishing cloth using double distilled water as the lubricant. The activity of electrode was tested using solu-

Scheme 2. Synthesis of complex.

tion of ferricyanide/ferrocyanide in 0.1 M KCl²⁰. The stock solutions of amino acid ketimine (5 mM) was prepared in methanol. Britton-Robinson buffer, phosphate buffer were prepared in doubly distilled water. In the typical cyclic voltammetric experiment, reaction mixture consisted of compound solution, methanol (the minimum volume necessary to keep the compound in the solution) and buffer solution (keeping the overall volume constant 10 ml). Before recording the current voltage curve, the solution was deoxygenated by purging a stream of nitrogen gas for 15 min prior to the experiments in order to remove dissolved oxygen from the media. The three electrodes (glassy carbon electrode as working, platinum as counter and Ag-AgCl electrode as reference electrode) were connected to the electrochemical cell. Required potential, scan rates, current sensitivity, initial potential and final potential were applied and resulting current measured as a function of applied potential.

The kinetic parameters such as charge-transfer coefficient (α_n), diffusion coefficient ($D_0^{1/2}$) and rate constant ($K_{f,h}^\circ$) have been calculated for irreversible and diffusion controlled reduction using following equations and reported in Tables 1–4.

$$|E_p - E_{p/2}| = \frac{1.857RT}{\alpha_n F} \left(\frac{47.7}{\alpha_n} \right) \text{mV} \quad (1)$$

$$I_p = 3.01 \times 10^5 n(\alpha_n)^{1/2} ACD_0^{1/2} \nu^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$E_p = -\frac{RT}{\alpha_n F} \left[0.78 + \ln \left(\frac{D_0^{1/2}}{K_{f,h}^\circ} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_n F \nu}{RT} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (3)$$

In vitro antibacterial and antifungal assay :

The biological activities of synthesized GMAPI ketimine and its Co^{II} metal complex has been studied for their antibacterial and antifungal activities by agar and potato dextrose agar diffusion method respectively. The antibacterial and antifungal activities were done at 20, 40, 60 and 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentrations in DMF solvent using two bacteria (*B. subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*) and two fungi (*Fusarium oxysporium* and *P. chrysogenum*) by the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) method. These bacterial strains were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and fungi strains were incubated for 48 h at 37 °C. Standard antibacterial (Ciprofloxacin) and antifungal drug (Ketoconazole) were used for comparison under similar conditions. Activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the zone showing complete inhibition (mm).

Table 1. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine in DMF-BR buffer at different pH (3, 5 and 7)

pH	ν (mV s^{-1})	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μA)	$E_{p/2}$ (mV)	$I_{pc}/\nu^{1/2}$	α_n	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^3$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$K_{f,h}^\circ$ (cm s^{-1})
3.0	50	-863.13	6.37	-302.92	0.90	0.08515	26.31541	1.335184×10^{-4}
	100	-874.17	9.4	-409.31	0.95	0.10261	22.03035	0.92319×10^{-4}
	150	-881.39	10.6	-381.90	0.91	0.0955	24.48208	1.503269×10^{-4}
	200	-900	10.7	-384.21	0.84	0.09248	23.57746	1.70647×10^{-4}
	250	-906.31	13.7	-388.41	0.86	0.0921	32.20845	2.57683×10^{-4}
5.0	50	-896.97	11.4	-778.62	1.61	0.40297	25.14186	3.7305×10^{-4}
	100	-913.57	12.5	-748.88	1.25	0.28964	22.54883	0.001746×10^{-4}
	150	-929.05	13.3	-754.92	1.08	0.2739	21.34328	0.002921×10^{-4}
	200	-938.17	13.28	-521.21	0.939	0.1144	21.80868	0.686794×10^{-4}
	250	-951.72	14.36	-501.21	0.99	0.10588	25.71511	1.124577×10^{-4}
7.0	50	-923.47	17.8	-524.84	2.51	0.10179	17.86783	0.337902×10^{-4}
	100	-963.53	16.1	-498.75	1.61	0.10262	17.04609	0.499628×10^{-4}
	150	-995.23	20.82	-501.20	1.70	0.09655	22.57557	0.87625×10^{-4}
	200	-1059.5	21.02	-514.23	1.48	0.08746	22.37031	2.507593×10^{-4}
	250	-1016.7	21.31	-548.23	1.30	0.10197	24.76793	3.896248×10^{-4}

Table 2. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine in DMF-phosphate buffer at different pH (5.8, 7 and 8)

pH	ν (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μ A)	$E_{p/2}$ (mV)	$I_{pc}/\nu^{1/2}$	α_n	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	$K_{f,h}^\circ$ (cm s ⁻¹)
5.8	50	-859.57	9.02	-347.25	1.276	0.09310	26.31541	1.082411×10^{-4}
	100	-881.39	10.6	-361.4	1.06	0.09173	22.03035	0.871204×10^{-4}
	150	-929.97	14	-337.79	1.103	0.08638	24.48208	1.980528×10^{-4}
	200	-938.15	15.6	-388.18	1.143	0.08673	23.57746	1.777059×10^{-4}
	250	-997.9	23.4	-427.72	1.46	0.08365	32.20845	2.454833×10^{-4}
7.0	50	-880.4	10.02	-501.44	1.41	0.12587	25.14186	0.362484×10^{-4}
	100	-889.99	10.9	-374.81	1.09	0.09258	22.54883	1.192573×10^{-4}
	150	-910	12.7	-400	1.03	0.09352	21.34328	1.250406×10^{-3}
	200	-930	14.3	-370	1.04	0.08518	21.80868	1.771277×10^{-4}
	250	-960.71	18.61	-386.08	1.17	0.08301	25.71511	2.257939×10^{-4}
8.0	50	-912.05	12	-778.6	1.61	0.35744	17.86783	0.9405×10^{-4}
	100	-929.05	13.31	-731.61	1.16	0.24158	17.04609	0.5761×10^{-4}
	150	-951.72	14.3	-501.67	1.13	0.10598	22.57557	0.762075×10^{-4}
	200	-963.53	16.1	-498.7	1.13	0.10262	22.37031	0.927277×10^{-4}
	250	-995.231	19	-483.83	1.20	0.09327	24.76793	1.385212×10^{-4}

Table 3. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine in CH₃OH-phosphate buffer at different pH (5.8, 7 and 8)

pH	ν (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μ A)	$E_{p/2}$ (mV)	$I_{pc}/\nu^{1/2}$	α_n	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	$K_{f,h}^\circ$ (cm s ⁻¹)
5.8	50	-607.10	8.90	-368.45	1.20	0.19987	17.72182	2.1367×10^{-5}
	100	-626.95	10.5	-415.51	1.05	0.2256	13.91557	0.8148×10^{-4}
	150	-673.60	14.7	-438.60	1.20	0.20298	16.76964	0.9383×10^{-4}
	200	-687.91	14.7	-437.97	1.00	0.19084	14.97761	2.3963×10^{-4}
	250	-695.76	14.5	-406.60	0.91	0.16496	14.21305	4.4963×10^{-4}
7.0	50	-680.00	7.10	-390.00	1.00	0.16448	15.58441	2.4675×10^{-4}
	100	-687.26	9.40	-427.47	0.94	0.18361	13.80884	1.864×10^{-4}
	150	-698.53	11.0	-412.77	0.85	0.16692	13.83776	3.1768×10^{-4}
	200	-740.19	13.5	-449.49	0.95	0.16409	14.83403	3.2266×10^{-4}
	250	-769.69	15.5	-451.48	0.98	0.14991	15.93788	4.6934×10^{-4}
8.0	50	-751.85	13.8	-463.68	1.90	0.16553	30.1951	2.9350×10^{-4}
	100	-761.88	15.3	-467.28	1.53	0.16191	23.93458	3.3962×10^{-4}
	150	-777.40	15.7	-458.99	1.20	0.14957	20.86421	4.5783×10^{-4}
	200	-794.06	18.5	-485.58	1.30	0.15463	20.94079	4.1989×10^{-4}
	250	-815.34	21.2	-495.13	1.34	0.14899	21.91732	5.0758×10^{-4}

Results and discussion

The cyclic voltammetric results for GMAPI ketimine and Co^{II} complex are reported in Tables 1–4 and their voltammograms are shown in Figs. 1–5.

Most of cyclic voltammograms were recorded with an initial potential E_i value +1000 and final potential

value E_s -1500 mV for GMAPI ketimine and E_i value +300 and switching potential value E_s -1000 mV for complex at the scan rates 50–250 mV/s, keeping the pH and the concentration of solution constant. The various parameters employed to evaluate the electrochemical reversibility are listed in the Tables 1–4.

Table 4. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of Co^{II} complex of glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine in DMF-NaClO₄ at different concentration

Complex conc. (mM)	ν (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	$E_{p1/2}$ (mV)	$I_{p,c}$ (μ A)	$I_{pc}/\nu^{1/2}$
1	50	-725.01	-560.07	15.9	2.24
	100	-696.13	-610.31	10.54	1.054
	150	-710.87	-613.20	14.64	1.19
	200	-711.75	-582.40	17.82	1.263
	250	-715.57	-621.42	21.09	1.35
2	50	-676.18	-609.86	11.42	1.615
	100	-699.85	-610.84	10.78	1.078
	150	-705.37	-626.23	18.35	1.49
	200	-726.16	-641.56	24.14	1.910
	250	-742.37	-646.73	28.70	1.81
3	50	-693.75	-635.93	15.86	2.24
	100	-707.80	-641.581	19.12	1.91
	150	-728.60	-653.31	24.51	1.73
	200	-738.29	-661.053	29.9	2.11
	250	-744.85	-665.68	31.5	1.99
4	50	-701.16	-641.48	23.04	2.23
	100	-709	-649.38	28.56	2.81
	150	-720.12	-656.71	32.23	2.60
	200	-735.42	-664.38	36.77	2.67
	250	-746.03	-673.13	42.30	1.71

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of GMAPI in methanolic medium containing phosphate buffer (pH 5.8).

The voltammograms show two irreversible reduction peak at all scan rates. The first peak (about -350 mV) may most probably be due to the reduction of -C=N- (azomethine) group of the adsorbed molecule and the second cathodic peak (about -700 mV) was thought to be due to the reduction of -C=N- group of the molecule in solution²¹. The peak potential value

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of GMAPI in methanolic medium containing phosphate buffer (pH 7).

shifted in the more negative direction with an increase in the scan rate indicating the electrochemical process was irreversible. The peak potential shift was higher when the scan rate increased. This means that under these conditions the electrochemical process is more irreversible. Peak current also increases as the scan

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of GMAPI in methanolic medium containing phosphate buffer (pH 8).

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of Co^{II} complex of GMAPI in methanolic medium 1–4 mM conc. at 250 scan rate.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammograms of Co^{II} complex (1 mM) of GMAPI in DMF medium at different scan rate.

rate increased for all the compounds. The linear nature of I_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ plot with an intercept different to zero shows that the reduction of GMAPI is diffusion controlled (Fig. 6)^{22,23}.

Fig. 6. Current (I_{pc}) vs $v^{1/2}$ of GMAPI in methanolic medium containing phosphate buffer (pH 5.8).

The effect of pH upon the reduction of GMAPI was investigated (Tables 1–3 and Fig. 7). Peak potential values of the compounds are found to be changed with the pH value of the solution. This dependence of the peak potential on pH indicating that proton transfer also takes place in the electrode reaction. The peak potential shifts in more negative values depending upon the pH of the solution. This means that the reduction is easier in acidic media and difficult in media where the proton concentration is low. The ease of reduction

Fig. 7. Potential vs scan rate in methanolic medium containing phosphate buffer (pH 5.8, 7.0 and 8).

is found to be more in acidic pH than in alkaline pH which may be because of the formation of easily reducible protonated intermediate.

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in two different medium DMF-phosphate buffer and CH₃OH-phosphate buffer. It was observed that the peak potential shifted to more negative values in presence of aprotic solvent (DMF) and magnitude of shift depends on the nature of solvent. The order of shift observed in present study is DMF-phosphate > CH₃OH-phosphate buffer. This trend parallels the trend in viscosity of solvent (DMF – 0.796 > methanol – 0.544)^{24,25}.

The effect of buffer solutions (BR buffer and phosphate buffer) upon the reduction of GMAPI was investigated. Peak potential values of the compound are found to be changed with the buffer solution. Phosphate buffer is more polar than BR buffer because of more ionization of component of phosphate buffer. Phosphate buffer consists of strong acid and strong base solution and BR buffer consists of comparatively weak acid (i.e. acetic acid) so phosphate buffer is more polar than BR buffer. This dependence of the peak

potential on buffer solution indicating that ionization of buffer also takes place in the electrode reaction. The peak potential shifts in less negative values depending upon the polarity of the buffer solution. This means that the reduction is easier in more polar buffer solution (phosphate buffer) and difficult in less polar buffer solution (BR buffer) where the ionization is low as evident from the Tables 1–3 at pH 7.

In this process imine group (-C=N-) 4-methylacetophenone glycine amino acid reduced into amine group (-C=NH₂⁺) in protic solvent such as CH₃OH. Since all steps involved in reaction mechanism take place at the same potential, there occurs a single reduction peak corresponding to transfer of two electrons (Scheme 3).

In the case of complex no anodic peak could be realised indicating towards the irreversible nature of electrode process. The nature of electrode was also confirmed from the peak potential value shifted in the more negative direction with an increase in the scan rate. Peak current also increases as the scan rate increased for the compounds. Effect of concentration on

Scheme 3. Proposed reduction mechanism for glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine (GMAPI).

the reduction potential was studied by varying the concentration of compound from 1 mM to 4 mM at the different scan rate. It was observed that the peak potential (E_{pc}) were shifted towards more negative values and the cathodic peak current was found to increase linearly as the compound concentration increased. The plot of I_{pc} vs concentration shows linearity, further indicating the electrode process were diffusion controlled. This kind of shift in E_{pc} in the cathodic direction with increasing concentration indicating that the reduction products are adsorbed over the electrode surface, this kind of shift has been predicted theoretically and observed experimentally²⁶.

Infrared study :

Absence of a $\nu(C=O)$ band (1740 cm^{-1}) of ketone and presence of $\nu(C=N)$ band occurs at $1630\text{--}1638\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of ligand indicates the condensation between ketonic group and amino group of amino acid. In comparison with the spectra of the GMAPI, the Co^{II} complex exhibited the band of $\nu(C=N)$ in the region $1600\text{--}1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$, showing the shift of the band

to lower wave number indicating that the nitrogen is coordinated to the metal ion. The broad and strong band present in the IR spectra of kitimine in the region $3200\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappear in the complex formation. The appearance of new bands in the region $610\text{--}628$ and $422\text{--}440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assign able to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively reflects the bonding of the metal ions to oxygen and nitrogen atoms²⁷.

In vitro antimicrobial assay :

The antimicrobial results are systematized in Tables 5 and 6.

It is evident from the results that, the biological activity of the metal complex is higher than the GMAPI ligand. This enhancement in the activity of the metal complex can be explained on the basis of chelation theory. It is, however, known that the chelating tends to make the kitimine act as more powerful and potent antimicrobial agents, thus inhibiting the growth of bacteria and fungi more than the parent kitimine GMAPI²⁸⁻³⁰.

Table 5. Antifungal studies of ketimine GMAPI and its Co^{II} complex

Antifungal Stock conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>				<i>P. crysogenum</i>			
	GMAPI		Co^{II} complex		GMAPI		Co^{II} complex	
	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index
20	16	0.72	14	0.636	4	0.18	6	0.27
40	18	0.81	18	0.81	6	0.27	8	0.36
60	25	1.13	24	1.09	8	0.36	12	0.54
80	28	1.27	22	1.00	11	0.5	14	0.63

Table 6. Antibacterial studies of ketimine GMAPI and its Co^{II} complex

Antibacterial Stock conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>				<i>Escherichia coli</i>			
	GMAPI		Co^{II} complex		GMAPI		Co^{II} complex	
	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Activity index
20	14	0.70	12	0.6	4	0.20	8	0.40
40	8	0.40	15	0.75	10	0.40	4	0.20
60	12	0.60	14	0.7	9	0.45	4	0.20
80	16	0.80	16	0.8	9	0.45	11	0.55

Conclusion

The results pertaining to Co^{II} complex is presented in Table 4. The explanation for the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process was same as that for other complexes.

In solutions of 1–4 mM, a single cathodic peak was observed at all scan rates. The peak potential and peak currents increase with the scan rate. Irreversible nature of the process was confirmed by the absence of anodic peak in the reverse scan.

Keeping in view of feasibility of the site of reduction and on the basis of cyclic voltammetric results, the reduction mechanism shown in Scheme 3 may be suggested for electro reduction of above studied glycine 4-methylacetophenonimine (GMAPI). The mechanism finds supports from the E_{pc} and $E_{p1/2}$ shifts towards negative potential with pH, as protons are consumed in the reduction, scan rate and concentration of compounds. GMAPI as well as its Co^{II} complex were the irreversible nature of the reduction. Antimicrobial activities of complex is more as comparison of GMAPI, which indicates that's metallation increases the biological activity.

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